

Atlantis

HOPES AND FUTURES OF ACADEMIA:
REIMAGINING BACON'S NEW ATLANTIS

NEW ATLANTIS 4.0

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Short Description
<p><i>The New Atlantis 4.0 is a speculative fable produced as a deliverable of the ATLANTIS project, written in deliberate homage to Francis Bacon's unfinished 1626 text. A voyager's report from a fictional Commonwealth, it reimagines the university as an assembled institution held together by continuous care rather than by any single governing logic. The piece draws on the project's empirical material and serves as a companion to the academic paper "Reassembling the University: Moral-Epistemic Configurations and Contested Futures."</i></p>

History of changes

Version	Date	Summary

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PREFACE

When I proposed this piece as one of the deliverables of the ATLANTIS project, I imagined producing a narrative capable of carrying a strong vision of what universities might yet become, four hundred years after Bacon. I labelled it 4.0 in the proposal, borrowing the language of Industry 4.0, to signal that this was not an exercise in nostalgia but an attempt to reimagine the university under the contemporary conditions that label names, such as platformisation, artificial intelligence, data-driven governance, and the entanglement of knowledge with digital infrastructures that are reshaping what institutions can be.

Yet, roughly halfway through the project, I began to realise two things. First, it was not simply difficult to extract visions of the future in the Baconian mode. For many interlocutors, imagining fundamentally different futures for the university was itself difficult. Their accounts remained anchored in crisis, constraint, and reforms they felt palpable. Even those most dissatisfied with the present often struggled to describe alternatives beyond better funding, less bureaucracy, or more time for research and teaching. The difficulty of imagining otherwise became one of the project's central findings.

Second, there was no single vision of the university's future waiting to be distilled from the material. There were many, and they did not reconcile. The project's interlocutors and interviewees articulated hopes that pulled in genuinely incompatible directions: toward scientific acceleration and toward slow scholarship, toward stronger public accountability and toward protection from the managerial logics that accountability so often becomes, toward humanistic renewal and toward a post-anthropocentric reimagining that treats the humanistic tradition itself as part of what needs amending.

There is an academic paper, currently titled "Reassembling the University", that develops this argument through four moral-epistemic configurations. But these are not four steps toward a synthesis. They are four partly overlapping, partly conflicting grammars through which universities have long been assembled, and through which their futures continue to be imagined.

A single unified vision would therefore have misrepresented what the project found. It would have required me to choose one configuration and grant it the authority of fiction, while pretending the others were not also present in my empirical material. The seductive thing about the Baconian form is precisely that it offers authority: the single speaking voice, the completed system, the imagined polity, the clear vision and mission. It carries the progressive, nature-conquering assumptions of modernity, many of which lie behind our present troubles.

So this piece attempts something different. It still borrows Bacon's formal elements, the voyager's report, the House of Learning, the guide who explains its workings. But the House it describes is not a solution. It is an assemblage. Its coherence lies not in its design but in its continuous maintenance. Its offices multiply rather than consolidate. Its central figure holds no executive authority and describes her role only as remembrance: keeping the relations between the parts from breaking.

In this spirit, the piece also attempts to amend what I take to be some of the most consequential blind spots of Bacon's original. Not because the original was a poor text, it was an astonishing one, but because it was, inevitably, an artefact of its time. Three amendments seemed especially necessary.

The first concerns gender. Bacon's *New Atlantis* is governed by a Father of Salomon's House and populated almost entirely by men. Its few women appear mainly in ceremonial or reproductive roles. This is not incidental to the vision. The authority of early modern natural philosophy was explicitly gendered, and its metaphors of nature as a female body to be interrogated, uncovered, and mastered were neither accidental nor harmless. Feminist STS scholars have shown how deeply these metaphors shaped what counted as knowledge and who counted as a knower. In this contemporary version, the presiding figure is a Mother, but the office is deliberately stripped of command. She remembers, she

does not rule. The gesture is intended less as a reversal than as a displacement of the paternal authority that organised Bacon's original.

The second concerns the relation to the non-human world. Bacon's House exists to enlarge "the bounds of Human Empire, to the effecting of all things possible". It is a phrase that has been cited approvingly for four centuries, and one that names, with unusual candour, the extractive horizon within which modern scientific institutions were founded. We now inhabit the consequences of that horizon. This version of *New Atlantis* cannot simply repeat Bacon's formula, but neither can it reject it outright, since so much of what universities do still depends on the infrastructures that formula built. What the Mother says instead, that the purpose of knowledge is not dominion but continuance, not to triumph over the world but to learn how to remain within it, is an attempt to name a different horizon without pretending we have already arrived there.

The third concerns finality. Bacon's Salomon's House is presented as an achieved institution whose workings the voyager merely records. "The Assembly" in this version is always under repair. This is not a stylistic preference. It follows directly from one of the project's central findings: universities are not fixed institutions in crisis, but assembled institutions whose coherence has always depended on ongoing work. It is precisely this work that is currently under strain because one configuration, the managerial, has grown to colonise the others. The catalogue of offices in the second half of the fable is therefore not a blueprint. It is a description of the kinds of labour a House would have to keep doing, permanently and without finality, in order to remain what it claims to be.

A final word on method. The fable draws on interview material without citing it directly. Phrases, images, and arguments offered by ATLANTIS interlocutors have been absorbed into the voice of the Mother and her Fellows. The academic paper currently titled "Resembling the University" can be read as a companion piece in which each configuration is traced back to its empirical and theoretical sources. The writing also involved sustained experimentation with generative AI tools, which are, after all, becoming new interlocutors in the work of synthesis, reformulation, and stylistic variation. They were used to test the Baconian register, redraft passages, and think through the new catalogue of offices and roles in ways that made the House feel more internally coherent. The question this raises is continuous with the heart of the project itself, since ATLANTIS has been, in part, a study of how knowledge is assembled, mediated, and made collectively under conditions where the boundary between human and machinic contribution is no longer clean.

I leave the piece, as the voyager leaves his report, unfinished. Not because the work is complete, but because the university itself remains unfinished: always assembled, always repaired, always contested, and always still becoming.

THE NEW ATLANTIS 4.0

A Work Unfinished

We sailed many weeks through a restless sea, our instruments uncertain and our charts of little use, for the currents in that quarter run crosswise, and the air is thick with vapours that confound both compass and star.

Our ship had been provisioned for discovery, yet we found ourselves instead undone by it. The engines of navigation failed us one by one. The sky burned white by day and gave no constellations by night. At last our fresh water spoiled, and several among us fell sick of fever and of that graver malady which has no name in the physicians' books, being a weariness of purpose and a mistrust of every chart we had been taught to follow.

We judged ourselves lost.

On the seventh morning, when hope was at its thinnest, a young sailor cried out from the foredeck that he had seen birds wheeling low, and soon after, a dark line upon the horizon.

Land.

Yet it did not appear as other coasts do, wild or ragged, but composed, almost gardened, as if the shore itself had been kept.

We drifted nearer under little sail and saw terraces cut into the cliffs, orchards in ordered rows, and, set back from the water, certain long low buildings of stone and glass that caught the sun like still pools. Between them moved people, though not in haste, and not idly, but with the quiet purpose of those about their daily offices.

Before we could lower a boat, a small vessel came out to meet us, swift and narrow, rowed by six. Those within wore plain garments of grey and blue. No arms. No banners. Only a device stitched upon their sleeves, a small knot or weaving of threads.

They hailed us courteously, yet would not at first permit us to land. One among them, who spoke our tongue with great ease, said:

“Be not afraid. This island receives strangers with care, not suspicion. Yet we must know first your condition, for we account health a matter not of the body alone but of the whole commonwealth.”

They asked after our illnesses, our stores, our place of departure, and whether we fled war or plague. When they were satisfied we carried no great contagion, they furnished us with fresh water, fruit, and certain draughts that restored our strength with surprising speed. After some consultation among themselves, they granted us leave to come ashore, though only a few at a time.

Thus we first set foot upon that land.

We expected noise and confusion, as in most ports. Instead, we found a great stillness. Not emptiness, but a kind of composed attention.

The streets were broad and shaded with trees. Water ran in small channels beside the paths. Workshops stood open to the air. In one place, we saw men and women gathered about a long table covered in instruments of glass and brass. In another, youths read aloud to one another beneath a colonnade. Farther on, several elders tended what appeared to be both a garden and an archive, for tablets and plants were kept side by side, each carefully labelled.

No one shouted. No one hurried. Yet nothing seemed neglected. It was as though the whole city laboured, but without frenzy.

We remarked also that there were no great houses of rank, nor towers of wealth set apart from the rest. The buildings differed in purpose, but not in dignity.

After we had been lodged and given clean garments, our guide told us:

“You have come, though by mischance, to the Commonwealth of the New Atlantis. Here we hold that knowledge is not the ornament of a few, but the maintenance of all. Therefore the greater part of our city is given over not to trade nor to spectacle, but to inquiry, to learning, and to care.”

This struck us as strange, for in our own lands such pursuits are often confined to a corner, or else made to serve whichever power has most recently purchased them.

The next day, we were told that one of the chief keepers of their institution would receive us and answer our questions.

We were brought at dawn along a shaded way toward the heart of the settlement. There stood no palace, nor temple, but a wide low complex built around several gardens and courts. Glass roofs admitted the light. Doors stood open on every side. People entered and departed freely, carrying tools, books, baskets of soil, and curious devices that hummed softly as they moved.

Our guide said only:

“This is the Assembly.”

We asked, “Is this your university?”

He smiled at the word, as if it were too narrow.

“It is the place where we keep the relations between things.”

We were led into a cool hall lined with tables of wood and stone. Upon the walls hung charts, not only of stars and seas, but of rivers, migrations, languages, and what seemed to be kinships between plants, animals, and machines alike.

After some time, there entered a woman of advanced years, though of strong and steady bearing. Her hair was silver, bound simply. Her clothing was plain, yet all present inclined their heads to her, not in fear, but in recognition.

She carried no emblem of rank. Only a small bundle of papers and a gardener's knife at her belt.

Our guide spoke softly.

“This is the Mother of the House.”

She greeted us not as subjects nor as petitioners, but as travellers long expected.

“Welcome,” she said. “You have come far, and perhaps farther than you intended. Rest yourselves. Then you shall see what it is we keep here, and why.”

And when we were seated among her Fellows, she began to explain the nature of their Assembly. She looked upon us for a moment, as if weighing not our rank or nation, but our weariness. Then she said:

“You are welcome among us. Yet before you ask what this place may give you, you must understand what it is we tend here. For this House is not founded to display wonders, nor to command nature, but to keep the world from coming apart.”

Her voice was low and even, and those nearby continued their labours as she spoke, so that her authority seemed not to interrupt the life of the place, but to flow within it.

“In your countries,” she said, “you build Houses of Learning as you would build fortresses or treasuries. You store knowledge there, and appoint some to guard it, and others to purchase it.

Thus learning becomes either a weapon or a commodity. We account it neither. We account it a relation.”

She beckoned us to follow.

We passed first into a long gallery open to the morning air. Upon the tables stood instruments of strange design. Some were lenses and mirrors, others small engines that flickered with light, and others yet made a quiet counting sound, like rain upon a roof.

Men and women worked beside them together, speaking little, though from time to time one would call another to look, and several would gather, not to compete, but to consider.

“These,” said the Mother, “are our seekers of causes. In former ages, such persons desired chiefly the mastery of nature. They spoke of conquest and dominion, as though the world were an enemy city. We have learned otherwise. For the earth is not conquered. It is only damaged.”

She placed her hand upon one of the humming engines.

“With these devices we are able to reckon patterns too great or too small for the unaided mind. They help us see the spread of fevers, the warming of the seas, the failing of soils, and many other motions hidden from ordinary sight. Yet we forbid these engines to decide for us what is worth knowing. They are servants only. Never judges.”

I remarked that in our lands such instruments were often used to hasten production and profit.

At this she smiled slightly. “Haste is sometimes mercy, sometimes violence. Therefore we ask always: who benefits from the speed?”

One of the Fellows beside her, a young woman with ink upon her fingers, added:

“We have a saying here. *The machine may run faster than judgment, but it may not run before it.*”

The Mother nodded, and led us on.

From there she led us not upward into towers, as we expected, but downward into a shaded court surrounded by cloisters.

Here the air was cool and still. People sat alone or in small groups with books and tablets. Some read aloud. Others wrote slowly by hand. No engines sounded. No bells rang. We had the curious impression of time thickening, like honey.

“These are our quiet rooms,” she said. “In every age, there are forces that would make thought run faster than judgment. Messages multiply. Opinions harden. Numbers speak louder than words. If we permit only the quick, we become foolish. So we keep places where nothing need be delivered, nothing measured, nothing displayed. Here one may spend a day upon a single page, or a year upon a single question.”

She paused, and added:

“We have found that without such slowness, all the rest becomes dangerous.”

Several young scholars approached her with notes. She read them carefully, asked a question or two, and returned them with thanks, as though they had given her a gift rather than completed an assignment.

I asked whether these were students.

“They are apprentices to judgment,” she said. “We do not train them only to solve problems, but to live with consequences. For a mind that has never learned to wait with a difficult thing will run, when the hour comes, in whatever direction is loudest.”

I asked further whether such slowness could be afforded, given the pressures of the age.

She answered, “In your world you say you cannot afford it. In ours we have found we cannot survive without it. These are not the same accounting.”

We continued.

Next she showed us certain offices that surprised us most of all. For instead of overseers with rods and ledgers, we found small groups seated around broad tables covered with charts and letters from distant towns. They spoke often with messengers and citizens who came freely through the doors.

“These,” she said, “are our stewards. You might call them managers. But their charge is not to command the Fellows. It is to keep faith with the people.”

Upon the walls hung tables of account, showing what food had been grown, what medicines prepared, what time and labour given to each undertaking.

“We make these reckonings public,” she said, “not that we may rank ourselves, but that all may see whether we are worthy of their trust. For knowledge that cannot answer to the world soon rots.”

One of the stewards rose to consult her about the repair of a roof damaged in the last storm. They spoke of timber, of cost, and of who might be displaced during the work. The matter seemed humble, yet it was treated with the same seriousness as any experiment.

I said quietly that in our universities such tasks are often thought beneath the dignity of learning.

She answered, “That is why your learning collapses so often. A house stands not by brilliance alone, but by maintenance.”

I asked then whether they also kept accounts of the sort my country calls *metrics*, being numbers by which scholars are judged and rewarded.

She looked at me with some curiosity. “We keep numbers, yes. But we use them as lamps, not as whips. A lamp shows you where you are. A whip tells you where to go. If you cannot tell the two apart, your house has already fallen, and only the noise of the whips disguises the silence.”

At last she brought us through a gate into what I can only describe as a garden, though it was unlike any garden we had known.

Beds of plants grew beside weather instruments. Children mapped insects while an elder recorded their findings. In one corner, several people examined samples of soil alongside what appeared to be records of law and of trade. The boundaries between field, laboratory, and library were nowhere clear.

“Here,” she said, “we teach the youngest among us. You divide knowledge into disciplines, as though the world itself were divided so neatly. But the river does not know it belongs to geology or to politics. The air does not choose between chemistry and history. So we teach them the knots first, not the threads.”

She knelt beside a group of youths who were cataloguing water from a nearby marsh. Before they began, each placed a hand upon the basin, and one spoke a few quiet words.

Seeing our curiosity, she said:

“They vow to treat what they study as kin. For when one imagines the world as mere resource, cruelty comes easily. But when one imagines it as family, one proceeds with care.”

I asked whether this was a ceremony of their religion.

“It is older than religion,” she said. “And younger also. For we have only lately relearned it, from those who never forgot.”

We walked some time in silence after that.

At length we returned to the central court where we had first met her.

“You have now seen most of our labours,” she said. “Though not all, for the Assembly is never complete. It is always under repair.”

“And you,” I asked, “are you the ruler of this House?”

She laughed softly.

“No. If I ruled it, it would fail within the year. I am called Mother not because I command, but because I remember. My office is to keep the relations between these parts from breaking. To remind the swift of the slow. The clever of the careful. The certain of the doubtful. The human of the more-than-human. That is all.”

She looked about the courts, where seekers, readers, stewards, and children crossed paths like threads in a loom.

“A university,” she said, “is not a machine for producing knowledge. It is a place where a society practises how to live together with what it comes to know. If we cease that practice, no discovery will save us.”

And hearing this, we began to understand that this Assembly was less a House than a continual weaving, and that its strength lay not in any single part, but in the care with which all were held together.

As we spoke with her, there came from a nearby court a low and steady murmur, unlike the voices of scholars or the wind in the leaves. It was a sound more regular, like many small clocks beating together.

Perceiving that we listened, the Mother said:

“You have heard our newest companions. Come. It is meet that you see them also, lest you think our work only pastoral and contemplative. We are not enemies of artifice.”

She led us into a broad hall roofed in glass and crossed with beams of copper. Along its length stood rows of cabinets and frames filled with wires, plates, and moving lights. Some shone softly as embers. Others flickered as though thinking. Before them sat several Fellows, though they touched the devices only lightly, more as one tends a fire than as one drives a horse. The air was warm, and carried the faint smell of metal after rain.

“These,” she said, “are our engines of reckoning.”

We asked whether they were instruments of calculation, like those used by navigators and merchants.

“They are that, and more besides. They keep for us patterns too vast for memory alone. They compare seasons across centuries. They trace the wandering of disease. They model the breaths of forests and the tempers of the sea. In former days, such engines were built chiefly for profit or for war. Now we bind them to another service.”

One of the Fellows called her over and showed a shifting map of colours that flowed like ink in water.

“What is it we see?” I asked.

“The heat of the earth,” she replied. “It tells us where crops will fail three summers hence, that we may prepare grain for those regions now.”

I confessed that in our lands such machines were said to replace scholars, or to judge them by number.

At this, several of the Fellows laughed outright. “If we let them judge us,” one said, “we should deserve the judgment.”

The Mother added: “These engines are quick, but foolish. They know nothing of mercy, nor of meaning. They only repeat, with great confidence, what they have been given. So we keep them close, as one keeps a strong animal. Useful in labour. Dangerous if left to roam.”

She showed us also certain walls where figures and tables were displayed for any to read.

“These are our public accounts. Here the people may see what we have done with their trust. How many hours spent, how many medicines prepared, how many fields restored. We use numbers as lamps, not as whips.”

This saying she repeated in our hearing more than once, as though she had learned, through long experience, that the distinction was easily forgotten.

When we left that hall, the light outside seemed gentler than before.

“You perceive,” she said, “that we do not reject the new arts. We only refuse to let any one logic rule the rest. For whenever one spirit grows too strong, the Assembly sickens.”

“And how do you prevent this?” I asked.

“By teaching the young otherwise from the beginning. Come, and you shall see their initiation.”

She brought us toward the gardens we had glimpsed earlier, where the paths widened into a green court. There gathered a company of youths, neither children nor yet fully grown, dressed plainly, each carrying a small satchel.

At the centre stood a basin filled with water, soil, seeds, and several curious objects that I later understood to be small recording devices.

An elder addressed them, but without sermon or grandeur. The Mother whispered to us: “This is their first vow.”

One by one, the youths stepped forward, placed their hands in the basin, and spoke their names aloud. Then each named something they would study that year. Some the river, some the market, some the air above the city, some the stories of the old, and one, I remember, the behaviour of the engines themselves.

After this, the elder said:

“Remember. What you study is not a thing apart from you. It is a relation. Treat it as you would your own kin.”

They answered together: “We will proceed with care.”

I asked whether this was symbolic only.

She looked at me with some surprise. “What is not symbolic?” Then, more gently: “If they learn first that knowledge is extraction, they will wound the world without noticing. If they learn first that knowledge is kinship, they hesitate. That hesitation saves much.”

Later we saw these same youths dispersed among the courts. Some worked beside the engines. Some read with the elders. Some measured soil. Some debated under the trees. None seemed confined to a single craft.

“We do not divide them too soon,” she said. “For once a mind is narrowed, it rarely widens again. The world's troubles are tangled. So their learning must be tangled also, at the root, before it may branch.”

By now the sun had declined, and the whole Assembly took on a golden light. Bells sounded softly, not to command labour's end, but to call people toward the common meal.

Scholars, stewards, gardeners, children, and we strangers all gathered at long tables. No rank separated them. The Mother sat not at the head, but among the youngest.

As bread was passed and wine poured, I asked her one last question.

“In our lands,” I said, “universities grow ever larger and yet seem ever more fragile. Their scholars are weary. Their purpose disputed. Their people distrust them. Yet here all seems whole. What is your secret?”

She considered for some time before answering.

“At the beginning,” she said, “your philosophers believed knowledge would give mankind power over nature. They were not wrong. But they forgot to ask what power would make of mankind. So their Houses grew strong, and their societies weak. We chose another foundation. We say the purpose of knowledge is not dominion, but continuance. Not to triumph over the world, but to learn how to remain within it.”

She looked across the tables, where laughter rose with the evening air.

“If ever we forget that, this place will become like yours. Full of brilliance, and empty of spirit.”

After supper, as the lamps were lit along the courts, I asked the Mother whether we had now seen the whole of their Assembly.

She shook her head. “You have seen only what the day allowed. The House is larger than any single telling. If you would have patience, I shall name some of the other offices, that you may carry at least their shape home with you, even if you cannot carry their substance.”

We sat upon a low bench beneath a fig tree, and she spoke as follows.

THE OFFICES OF THE ASSEMBLY

Being a Partial Catalogue, as Recited by the Mother upon the Evening of Our Arrival

“There are among us, first, the *Seekers of Causes*, whom you have seen. Their charge is to inquire into the hidden motions of nature, the spread of fevers, the breath of the forests, the temper of the seas. They labour with instruments and with number, and they are bound to no master save the question itself. We account them necessary, yet we do not let them rule, for a house ruled by questions alone becomes cold.

“There are the *Keepers of the Quiet Rooms*, who tend slowness as others tend a fire, lest it go out. They read. They write. They do nothing that can be shown in a ledger. Yet it is by them that the rest of us are kept from running foolish.

“There are the *Stewards*, who keep faith between the Fellows and the people. They reckon our stores and our labours, they answer to those who feed us, and they publish our accounts as one

would hang a lantern at the door. They do not command the learned. They serve them, and the city both. Where stewardship becomes command, we have found, the whole house hardens into a cage.

“There are the *Gardeners of Kinship*, who teach the youngest to treat what they study as family, and who bring together in one plot the plants and the engines and the old records of law. They do not respect the fences between disciplines, for they say the world itself does not know those fences.

“There are the *Tenders of Engines*, who keep our reckoning-machines in good order, and who speak with them as one speaks with a strong beast, firmly and without flattery. They know the engines' limits better than any, and so they are our chief protectors against those who would mistake the engine's speed for wisdom.

“There are the *Keepers of Failures*, whose charge is to remember what has not worked, and to tell the tale of it plainly, so that we may not repeat it. We honour them as much as any, for a house that forgets its errors commits them again, and with interest.

“There are the *Envoys of the Towns*, who go out yearly among the villages and the markets to learn what knowledge is needed there, rather than what we ourselves desire to pursue. They bring back the questions of the world, and lay them at our door. It is often uncomfortable.

“There are the *Menders of Instruments*, who repair what is broken rather than discarding it. We hold maintenance equal to invention, for we have seen that a civilisation which invents much and mends little soon drowns in its own brilliance.

“There are the *Translators*, who move between tongues and between crafts, so that no learning becomes solitary. The physician must understand the poet, and the poet the farmer, and the farmer the one who tends the engines, else each grows proud, and pride is the first sickness of the learned.

“There are the *Arbiters of the Orders*, who sit only in disputes between the several spirits of the House, lest any one grow too strong. When the Seekers would swallow the Quiet Rooms, or the Stewards would reduce the Gardeners to a line upon a ledger, these arbiters intervene. Their office is the hardest, and we rotate it often, for it wearies whoever holds it.

“There are the *Watchers of the Seas and Forests*, who observe the signs of distress in the world beyond our walls, and bring word of them within. They remind us, when we grow too pleased with our own order, that our order sits upon a larger one, which does not know or care for our arrangements, and which we are daily endangering.

“There are the *Makers of Utopias*, who are permitted, and indeed required, to imagine houses that do not yet exist, and cities that may never exist, and to draw maps of them, and to argue for them in full seriousness. We do this because we have found that a House which cannot imagine itself otherwise cannot correct itself. A people without utopias is a people already ruled.

“And there are many more besides, whom it would weary you to hear named. The Keepers of the Old Tongues. The Calendars. The Midwives of Difficult Conversations. The Readers of the Sky. The Watchers of the Children. Each office exists because at some moment in our history, a thing nearly broke, and the office was invented to hold it. We do not abolish these offices when the danger seems past, for the danger returns.”

She paused a moment, then added:

“You will perceive that no single one of these would serve, alone. The Seekers without the Quiet Rooms become reckless. The Quiet Rooms without the Stewards become indulgent. The Stewards without the Gardeners become tyrants of the ledger. The Gardeners without the Seekers become sentimental. Each office corrects the excess of another. Each depends upon the rest.

“In your lands, I am told, one such spirit has grown to eat the others. The counting-spirit, which you call management. It began as a servant, as ours did, and became a master, as ours has not been permitted to. You will know whether this is true.

“It is the whole labour of the House to keep this balance. And it is never achieved. Only practised.”

She spoke these things plainly, as though reciting the tasks of a household. I confess I could not keep pace with the number of them, nor fully understand how such variety did not dissolve into confusion. Yet nothing in that place seemed confused. Rather it was as if the Assembly lived by a continual weaving, each office taking up what another set down.

At length she said:

“Forgive me. To describe the whole would take longer than your stay. For we are always adding, always mending. By the time I had finished, it would already be otherwise.”

On the days that followed, they permitted us to move more freely about the courts. I will not pretend I understood all that I saw. There were rooms whose purpose I could not guess, and conversations whose subject I could not follow. I observed that the Fellows spoke often of things I had not thought belonged in a House of Learning at all, such as the repair of water-channels, the care of the old, the feeding of children, and the keeping of lost tongues. Yet these were treated with the same seriousness as questions of nature or of law.

I observed also that they were not without their difficulties. I saw a dispute between two Fellows upon a matter of method, which grew warm, and was settled only when an Arbiter was called. I heard one young scholar complain that the Stewards required of him a reckoning of his time that he found burdensome, and I heard a Steward reply, patiently, that the reckoning was not for judgment but for care, and that if he wished the reckoning abolished, he might propose it before the Assembly, and it would be heard. I did not learn the outcome.

I heard also, more than once, murmurs that their own House was under strain. That the world beyond their shore was growing harder. That certain neighbouring powers looked upon their manner of life with suspicion, and spoke of it, in their own councils, as a kind of excess, or a kind of weakness, or a kind of heresy. The Fellows did not conceal this from us. The Mother herself said one evening, as we walked beside a stream:

“Do not imagine us safe. We are not safe. No such House is safe. We have only chosen to spend our vulnerability upon things we believe worth being vulnerable for.”

And here my account grows imperfect. For the hour of our departure came sooner than we expected, our ship being now repaired and our company recovered, and there were many further chambers and gardens which we did not see.

What more they showed us on the following days I cannot faithfully set down. My notes from those hours are confused, and my memory mingles what I witnessed with what I was told, and what I was told with what I have since imagined. I do not think the Mother would mind this. She said to me, on the morning we left:

“Take home what you can. Misremember it kindly. A faithful copy would do no good. You must assemble the thing again, in your own country, with your own hands, and with such materials as you find there. Do not wait for a ship to bring you ours.”

She pressed into my hand the small woven device that each of them wore upon the sleeve, a knot of threads of many colours, none dominant, none separable.

“This is our only emblem,” she said. “We have no flag. We have no seal. Only this. And it is not a symbol of what we are. It is a reminder of what we must keep doing.”

I have it still.

Only this I know, that their House was not built to stand complete, but to remain in care. That its strength was not any single brilliance, but the refusal to let any single brilliance govern. That its quiet was not absence of labour, but the sound of labour that has found its measure.

And so I leave this relation unfinished, as I found it...